

**AMINOSPIRTLARNI PARACHALASH BILAN MONOAMINLAR VA
MANNIX REAKTSIYASI ASOSIDA DIAMINLAR SINTEZI.**

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Rezyume: Ushbu maqolada atsetilen aminospihlari asosida monoaminlar va Mannix reaksiyasi bo'yicha atsetilen, paraform va ikkilamchi aminlar ishtirokida diaminlar sintezi o'rganildi. Sintezlangan monoamin va diaminlarning tuzilishi, fizik –kimyo-viy doimiyligi va reaksiya unumi aniqlandi. Katalizator tabiatiga maxsulot unumi bog'liqligi o'rganildi. Sintezlangan maxsulotlarning tuzilishi IQ - va PMR – spektrlar bilan tasdiqlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: 3- N-dimetilaminopropin -1; 3-N- dietilaminopropin- 1; 1,4-di- (N,N-dimetilamino)butin -2; 1,4-di (N,N-dietilamino)-butin -2; Mannix reaksiyasi, infraqizil spektr, paramagnit rezonans, valent to'lqin tebranishi, deformatsion to'l-qin funktsiya, kondensatlanish reaksiyasi.

**СИНТЕЗ МОНОАМИНОВ С РАЗЛОЖЕНИЕМ АМИНОСПИРТОВ И
ДИАМИНОВ НА ОСНОВЕ РЕАКЦИИ МАННИХА**

Аннотация: В данной работе изучен синтез моноаминов на основе ацетиленовых аминспиртов и диаминов в присутствии ацетилена, параформа и вторичных аминов по реакции Манниха. Определены структура, физико-химические константы и условия образования синтезированных моноаминов и диаминов с высоким выходом. Обнаружена зависимость выхода продуктов от природы катализатора. Строение синтезированных продуктов подтверждено ИК- и ПМР-спектрами. Определены их физико-химические константы и выходы.

Ключевые слова: 3-N-диметиламинопропин -1; 3-N-диэтиламинопро-пин-1; 1,4-ди (N,N-диметиламино)бутин -2; 1,4-ди (N,N-диэтиламино) бутин -2, реакции Манниха, инфракрасный спектр, парамагнитный резонанс, коле-бание валентной волны, волновая функция деформации, реакция конденса-ции.

**SYNTHESIS OF MONOAMINES WITH DECOMPOSITION OF AMINO-
ALCOHOLS AND DIAMINES BASED ON THE MANNICH REACTION**

Annotation: In this work, the synthesis of monoamines based on acetylene amino alcohols and diamines in the presence of acetylene, paraform and secondary amines using the Mannich reaction was studied. The structure, physicochemical constants and conditions for the formation of synthesized monoamines and diamines with high yield were determined. The dependence of the products on nature of the catalyst was

discovered. The structure of the synthesized products was confirmed by IR and PMR spectra. Their physicochemical constants and yields were determined.

Key words: 3-N-dimethylaminopropine-1; 3-N-diethylaminopropyne-1; 1,4-(N,N-dimethylamino)butyne-2; 1,4-di(N,N-diethylamono)butyne-2, Mannish reactions, intrared spectrum, paramagnetic resonance, stretching wave vibration, deformation wave function, condensation reaction.

ASOSIY QISM. Monoaminlarni Mannix reaksiyasi asosida sintezlab bo'lmaydi, chunki monoamin yuqori unumda hosil bo'ladigan diaminlarga reaksiya muhitida aylanadi. Shu sababli, dastlab aminospirtlar sintezlandi [1,2,3] va aminospirtlarni termik parchalash yo'li bilan monoaminlar olindi. Katalizator sifatida KOH, Ba(OH)₂ va NaOH kukun holida va quruq xolatda ishlatildi. Katalizator tabiatining monoamin unumiga ta'siri o'rganildi [4,5,6,7]. Sintezlangan atsetilen aminospirtlarni katalitik parchalash yo'li bilan monoaminlarni sintezlash reaksiyasini umumiy xolda quyidagicha ifodalash mumkin :

bu yerda R= - CH₃; - C₂H₅; - N(R')₂ = - dimetilamino, - dietilamino, - piperidino, - morfolino guruh

Atsetilen diaminlari Mannix reaksiyasi bo'yicha sintezlandi va ularning hosil bo'lishini umumiy xolda quyidagicha ifodalash mumkin :

bu yerda - N(R')₂ = - dimetilamino, - dietilamino, - piperidino, - morfolino guruh

Mazkur ishning asosiy maqsadi atsetilen aminospirtlarini katalitik parchalash bilan monoaminlarni va Mannix reaksiyasi asosida atsetilendan diaminlarni sintezlash va fizik-kimyoviy xossalarini o'rganish iborat.

1-(N-dimetilamino)propin - 2 ning sintezi. 2,82 g (0,02 mol) 5-N-dimetil-amino-2-metilpentin-3-ol-2 va 0,08 g massali quruq, kukun xolatdagi bariy gidrok-sid bilan aralashmasi 50 - 60 °S temperaturada, 2- 3 soat davomida qizdirildi. Aralashma 50 ml xajmli dietil efirda ekstraksiya qilindi. Efirli qism potash bilan quri-tildi. Monoaminni ajratib olish uchun efir haydaladi va hosil bo'lgan monoamin diflegmatorli Klyayzen kolbasida (balandligi 15 sm) haydaldi. Reaksiyada 1,079 g (nazariy unumda 65-70 %) 1-(N-dimetilamino)propin- 2 hosil bo'ldi.

1,4-di(N,N -dietilamino)-butin -2 ning sintezi. Hajmi 500 ml uch og'izli kol-baga (mexanik aralashtirgich bilan jihozlangan), 0,73g (0,01 mol) dietilamin gidro-xlorid tuzi va 0,03 g (0,01 mol) paraformaldegid solinib 100 ml dioksanda eritildi. Aralashma elektr plitkasida 60 -70 °S temperaturada qizdirildi va aralashtirib turilgan xolda atsetilen gazining kuchli oqimi 3 -4 soat davomida o'tkazildi. Aralashmaga HCl eritmasidan 5 -6 tomchi tomizilib, polimer holdagi paraformaldegid

monomer holatga o'tkaziladi. Olingan qora rangli, og'ir massali suyuqliklar aralashmasi deflagmatorli kolbada haydaladi. Dastlab erituvchi dioksan haydab olinadi, qolgan aralashma vakuumda haydaladi. Reaksiyada 1,36 g (69.7 % unum bilan 1,4-di(N,N –dietilamino) -butin -2 hosil bo'ladi.

Sintezlangan mono va diaminlarning kimyoviy tuzilishi infraqizil spektr IQ, YAMR 13S va YAMR 1H metodi bilan tasdiqlandi. Sintezlangan 1-(N-dietilamino)propin- 2 da metil va metilen gruppalarining valent to'lqin tebranishiga xos yutilish chiziqlari $2975 - 2221 \text{ sm}^{-1}$ sohaga, $- \text{C}\equiv\text{C}$ gruppasining yutilish chizig'i $2325 - 2100 \text{ sm}^{-1}$ sohaga, $\equiv\text{C} - \text{H}$ gruppasi valent tebranishining yutilish chizig'i 3300 sm^{-1} sohaga mos keladi. Bundan tashqari spektrning 1400 sm^{-1} sohasi yaqinida metilen gruppaning deformatsion tebranishiga xos yutilish chizig'i ifodalagan.

Sintezlangan monoamin 1-morfolinopropin -2 ning IQ -spektrida $- \text{C}\equiv\text{C} - \text{H}$ guruhining valent to'lqin tebranishi 3250 sm^{-1} sohasida, $\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$ guruhi esa 2250 sm^{-1} sohada intensiv piklar yordamida ifodalangan.

1- N- piperidinopropin- 2 ning YAMR 13S spektrida $\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$ guruhi uglerod atomli yadrosiga tegishli intensiv chiziq $73,2 - 80 \text{ m.u.}$, sohada, piperidin xalqasidagi uglerod atomlari yadrosiga tegishli chiziqlar $24,3 - 26,2 \text{ m.u.}$ va $52,7 \text{ m.u.}$ sohada namoyon bo'lgan.

1,4 -di(N,N -piperidino)butin- 2 metilen gruppalarining valent to'lqin tebranish yutilish chizig'i $2950 - 2600 \text{ sm}^{-1}$, metilen guruhining deformatsion to'lqin tebranish yutilish chizig'i 1450 sm^{-1} sohada ifodalangan. Diamin molekulasida simmetrik bo'lganligi sababli, $- \text{C}\equiv\text{C}-$ gruppasi valent tebranish yutilish chizig'i $2200 - 2100 \text{ sm}^{-1}$ sohada namoyon bo'lmaydi.

1,4-di(N,N- piperidino)butin- 2 ning PMR 1H spektrida ikkita piperidin xalqasining metilen guruhiga tegishli signal $\delta 1,41 - 1.51 \text{ m.u.}(12 \text{ H})$ sohada va azot atomiga nisbatan α - holatda joylashgan piperidin xalqasining to'rtta metilen guruhiga tegishli signal $\delta 2,30 - 2.36 \text{ m.u.}(6\text{H})$ sohada, shuningdek $-\text{CH}_2-$ guruhidagi protonlarga tegishli signal $\delta 3.13 \text{ m.u.}(4\text{H})$ sohada ifodasini topgan.

Jadval I

Sintezlangan monoaminlarning fizik -kimyoviy domiyliklari.

No	Monoaminlar nomi va formulasi	Brutto formula si	Unumi, %	T. qayn.. °S/mm. sm..us.	n_D^{20}	d_4^{20}
1	1-N-dimetilamino-propin-2 $\text{HC}\equiv\text{CCH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$	$\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{N}$	65-70	79- 80	1,4175	0,7792
2	1-N-dietilamino-propin-2 $\text{HC}\equiv\text{CCH}_2\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2$	$\text{C}_7\text{H}_{13}\text{N}$	71,5	119-120	1,4296	0,8042
3	1-N-dibutilamino-propin-2	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}$	52,1	87-89/19	1.4600	0,8116

	$\text{HC} \equiv \text{CCH}_2\text{N}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$					
4	1-N-piperidino-propin-2 $\text{HC} \equiv \text{CCH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}$	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_{13}\text{N}$	70-78	72/35	1,4718	-
5	1-N-morfolino-propin -2 $\text{HC} \equiv \text{CCH}_2\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}$	$\text{C}_7\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}$	63-65	68/10	-	-

Jadval II

Sintelangan diaminlarning fizik- kimyoviy doimiyliklari

No	Diaminlar nomi va formulasi	Unum, %	T. qayn. °S/mm. sm.us.	n_D^{20}	d_4^{20}
1	1,4-di(N,N-dimetilamino)butin- 2 $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{NCH}_2\text{C} \equiv \text{CCH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$	51,3	178-179	1,4533	0,8660
2	1,4-di(N,N –dietilamino)butin -2 $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{CH}_2\text{C} \equiv \text{CCH}_2\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2$	69,7	220-221	1,4582	0,8013
3	1,4-di(N,N-dibutilamino)-butin-2 $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{NCH}_2\text{C} \equiv \text{CCH}_2\text{N}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$	74,4	180- 181/15	1,4563	0,862
4	1,4-di(N,N-piperidino) -butin -2 $\text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}\text{NCH}_2\text{C} \equiv \text{CCH}_2\text{NC}_5\text{H}_{10}$	70-80	149/3	1,4954	-
5	1,4- di (N,N-morfolino) -butin -2 $\text{OC}_4\text{H}_8\text{NCH}_2\text{C} \equiv \text{CCH}_2\text{NC}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}$	73-82	150/3	1,4931	-

Xulosa. Atsetilen spirtlarini parchalash asosida monoaminlarning yuqori unumda hosil bo'lishi atsetilen aminospirtlarining molekulyar massasiga bog'liq. Aminospirtning molekulyar massa ortishi bilan uning parchalanishi yuqori unumda sodir bo'ladi. 5-N-dimetilamino-2-metilpentin-3-ol-2 aminospirti 6-N-dimetil-amino -3- metilgeksin -4-ol-3 aminospirtiga qaraganda qiyin parchalanadi. Amino-spirtlar termik parchalanishi katalizatorga tabiatiga bog'liq. Kukun holatdagi bariy gidroksid (140°S) kaliy gidroksidga (160°S) ga qaraganda aminospirtlarni oson va yuqori unumda monoaminga aylantiradi. Natriy karbonat, kaliy karbonat tuzlari

ishtirokida aminospirtlarni parchalash monoaminlarning chiqish unumini pasayishini ko'rsatdi.

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